

VERIFICATION OF FAILURE PROCESS IN ACCELERATED TESTING METHOD

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SUMMARY

In order to establish more reliable accelerated testing methodology (ATM) for FRP laminates, failure process through the accelerated tests is verified by the “in-situ” precise observation method, which can trace the damage propagation behaviour more directly and simply than the previous approach. Bending load is applied to the specimen under various temperatures, and the difference of damage evolution behaviour on the edge of specimen is observed by optical microscope.

Keywords: failure process, in-situ observation, temperature, ATM, CFRP

INTRODUCTION

Over past 5 years, our research group has conducted the research works about the evaluation of “the accelerated testing methodology (ATM) for long-term durability and the damage tolerance performance of marine composites” (ONR Award Number: N000140110949). Here, ATM is known as the mechanical theory based on the “visco-elastic” behaviour of resin. Therefore the mechanical behaviour of FRP is also dominated by the visco-elastic property of matrix resin in the range of “visco-elastic” behaviour [1-5].

However, when ATM is extended to the estimation of “strength”, the validity of extended ATM should be verified empirically, because the failure process of FRP is sometimes different between at low and high temperatures, for example. Therefore, it is necessary to prove that the failure process is same at the variable temperatures.

The past researches about ATM and damage evaluation in our group were conducted in parallel with each other. For establishing more reliable ATM, it is important to clear theoretically and experimentally that the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP) holds for the damage growth under constant and cyclic loadings. Now, in order to verify the experimental validity of ATM, the difference of damage propagation behavior of FRP under variable temperatures was evaluated based on the damage observation techniques [6-7]. In this study, edge observation of the damage propagation under 3-point bending at variable temperatures was proposed and evaluated.

MATERIALS AND SPECIMENS

Material used in this study was T700/#2500 prepreg laminates. Stacking sequence of laminate was $[0/90_5/0/90_5/0]$, in which micro-cracking is generated easily in the 90° layers. Moulding method was hot-pressing. Thickness of laminate was 2.4mm. Specimen was cut to the geometry of 15mm in width and 70mm in length. Fig.1 shows photographs of specimen.

Fig.1 Photographs of specimen

TESTING METHOD

In order not only to generate transverse cracks in 90° layers, but to directly observe crack propagation behaviour on the edge surface, 3-point bending load was selected in this study. Static bending load was applied to the specimen under both room temperature and high temperature, and the difference of damage evolution behaviour was observed by optical microscope. Figure 2 shows a setup for in-situ damage observation.

Fig.2 Observation method of damage propagation

Testing condition was conformed to the Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS) K7074. Fulcrum span was 30mm, and loading speed was 1.0mm/min. In order to consider the effect of environmental temperature, 3-point bending test was conducted under both room temperature and 100°C. Here, glass transition temperature (T_g) of the target CFRP is 110°C. Therefore, the condition of 100°C is the temperature just below T_g of the target material.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Edge observation of damage propagation under room temperature

Figure 3 shows the stress-deflection curve of 3-point bending test under room temperature. Circles on the curve indicate points where fracture events were observed. Photographs of failure process observed along the test are shown in Fig.4.

At the point 1 in Fig.3, generation of first transverse crack was recognized, as shown in Fig.4 (1). Subsequently, transverse cracks were increased with increasing of load (Fig.4 (2)) up to the maximum load. At the point 3 in Fig.3, load indicated maximum value and then decreased suddenly. At this point, local buckling was observed just under the loading pin, as shown in Fig.4 (3). Thereafter, delamination was propagated drastically from the edge of transverse crack (Fig.4 (4)), and load was decreased drastically at the point 4 in Fig.3. This delamination was gradually propagated, and then rapid propagation was observed at the point 5 in Fig.3.

Fig.3 Load-deflection curve (under room temperature)

(1) Generation of first transverse crack.

(2) Increase of transverse cracks.

(3) Generation of buckling in surface 0° layer.

(4) Generation of delamination from the edge of transverse crack.

(5) Drastic propagation of delamination.

Fig.4 Photographs of damage propagation behaviour on the edge surface of specimen (under room temperature)

Edge observation of damage propagation under high temperature (100°C)

As well as the test under room temperature, damage propagation behaviour was observed through the test under 100°C environment. Figure 5 shows the stress-deflection curve of 3-point bending test. Photographs of failure process observed through the test are shown in Fig.6.

In this case, no damage was observed on the edge surface of specimen until the maximum load value was obtained, as shown in Figs.6 (1) and (2). Then, at the maximum load, indicated by the point 3 in Fig.5, local buckling was observed just under the loading pin, as shown in Fig.6 (3).

Fig.5 Load-deflection curve (under 100°C)

Environmental effect on the failure process

At room temperature, multiple transverse cracks were observed in 90° layer of tensile side. These transverse cracks were preceded by local buckling in 0° layer of compressive side. Stress condition in 90° layer was calculated based on the composite beam theory, as shown in Fig.7. Bending stress was 46.5MPa in the vicinity of interface between 0° and 90° layers of tensile side. This stress level is approximately 67% of 69MPa, which is tensile strength of 90° layer. One of the reasons why the stress level was remained at 67% of original strength is the existence of defects like void which can be observed on the edge surface of specimen in Fig.4. Compressive stress of 1454MPa, which was generated when the maximum stress was applied at 0° layer in compressive side, was good agreement with the compressive strength of 1470MPa.

On the other hand, local buckling occurred in 0° layer in compressive side without cracking, because Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness was increased with increasing temperature [8-10]. Additionally, because buckling strength was decreased with decreasing resin stiffness, local buckling was preceded by transverse cracking.

However, in these two cases, bending strength was determined by the generation of buckling in both cases, and the existence of micro-cracking hardly influenced the strength of specimen.

Therefore, when the determining factor of strength was buckling, even if crack propagation process was different between room and high temperatures, the validity of ATM is proved.

(1) No damage was observed.

(2) No damage was observed.

(3) Generation of buckling in surface 0° layer.

Fig.6 Photographs of damage propagation behaviour on the edge surface of specimen (under 100°C)

CONCLUSIONS

In order to establishing more reliable ATM, the difference of damage propagation behavior of FRP under variable temperatures was evaluated based on the damage observation techniques.

Static bending load was applied to the specimen under both room temperature and 100°C, and the difference of damage evolution behavior was observed by optical microscope. Because buckling was the dominant factor to determine bending strength, the validity of ATM was apparent in 3-point bending test.

The applicability of TTSP will be confirmed in the edge observation of damage propagation under 3-point bending. In the current study, there is a little number of samples to confirm the formation of TTSP. Proposed approach will be extended to the fatigue condition. Therefore, 'in-situ' damage observation apparatus under high temperature conditions should be developed, because current damage observation at high temperature is conducted intermittently.

Fig.7 Stress distribution in bending specimen

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